

Communication Strategies of Traditional Figures in Resolving of Dopofuleighoo (Elopement) Tradition in the Muna Ethnic Community in Muna Regency, Southeast Sulawesi

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Received: 11.04.2025 | Accepted: 16.04.2025 | Published: 22.05.2025

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15487062](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15487062)

Abstract

Original Research Article

This research aims to analyze the communication strategies of traditional figures in resolving the dopofuleighoo (elopement) tradition in the Katobu Sub-District, Muna Regency. This research uses a qualitative approach with informants of traditional figures, lebe (Mosque employers), families, and actors, and dopofuleighoo marriage officers in Muna Regency, who were selected purposively. Data collection techniques were through in-depth interviews and document studies. While data processing techniques refer to the data processing and preparation model in a qualitative research approach and data analysis techniques refer to domain and taxonomy analysis. The research results showed that traditional figures' communication strategies in resolving dopofuleighoo (elopement) tradition in the Muna ethnic community in Muna Regency use an informative and persuasive communication strategy from the beginning to the end. The informative strategy, namely simply conveying information (submission to the bride's family about the existence of dopofuleighoo while the persuasive strategy is to persuade, invite or influence both the family of the woman and the family of the man when they find problems in the process of settling dopofuleighoo (when discussing the amount of dowry and fines that must be paid). paid by the prospective groom. Persuasion is also used to influence the prospective woman's family to accept the girl's wish to marry her choice because the girl who will carry out domestic life is the girl herself. Therefore, the Muna traditional figures of the Muna ethnic community maintain communication with various traditional community groups in Muna Regency to do their roles well, even though some people of the Muna ethnic community do not want to do dopofuleighoo tradition.

Keywords: Dopofuleighoo, Communication Strategy, Muna Ethnic, Traditional Figures.

Citation: Larisu, Z., Dilla, S., Rajab, M., Joko, J., Iba, L., Herman, L. O., & Aso, L. (2025). Communication strategies of traditional figures in resolving of Dopofuleighoo (elopement) tradition in the Muna ethnic community in Muna Regency, Southeast Sulawesi. *SSR Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 114-120.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has various ethnic groups spread from Sabang to Merauke. Each ethnic group adheres to different marriage customs. Marriage is a permanent relationship between a man and a woman that is legally recognized by the community based on marriage regulations that apply to certain communities and is a necessity of life in society (Haris and Rahim, 2017). A legal marriage bond is proven by the existence of a marriage certificate or marriage book for husband and wife.

Marriage is generally carried out to form a family or is the beginning of a life together between a man and a woman (Lisnawati, 2022; Rubyasih, 2016). The form of marriage depends on the local culture and will be different

from other cultures. Some Indigenous communities carry out marriages by elopement, such as the Batak, Lampung, Bali, Sulawesi, and Maluku communities (Hadikusuma, 2003; Mukmin, et al., 2016; Ariana, 2016; Dian, 2016). In Aceh, especially the Gayo people elopement is called munik, Ambon calls lari bini, Toba Bataks are called Mangalua, Flores is called roko mating, in Bugis-Makassar calls it Silariang, Bali is called Ngerorod and many more other names of elopement terms in Indonesian society (Simanjuntak, 2017).

Elopement is a type of marriage that occurs when the prospective husband and wife run away without a formal proposal and engagement (Sudiyat, 2000). This is used as a solution so that the family can permit the couple to get married (Hadikusuma, 2003). According to

Soekanto (2005), several factors cause elopement carried out, such as the absence of approval from the guardian or both parents and family, the high dowry and forfeited money, and the factor of the woman being pregnant out of wedlock.

In Muna ethnic community in Muna Regency, Southeast Sulawesi, elopement is known as Dopofuleighoo. Dopofuleighoo (elopement) has long been carried out by the Muna ethnic community. Dopofuleighoo is mostly caused by the parents of the bride who do not approve of their daughter to marry with a man of her choice even though they have been dating for a long time. The most common reason the bride is considered immature while the groom cannot wait too long. Other reasons are the parents of the bride and groom wanting a big party, the difference in social status, the woman being pregnant before marriage, and the existence of a love triangle (Aso, L. et al, 2021).

Generally, elopement is an act that violates customary law, violates parental authority, and undermines the honor of the girl's parents and relatives (Hadikusuma, 2003). Likewise in the Muna ethnic community, elopement is considered a family disgrace (the girl no longer pays attention to parental orders or advice) and can cause slander (both bride and groom are considered to have committed acts that violate customary and religious laws). Therefore, elopement often leads to undesirable things such as parents not being willing to become guardians for their daughters and not infrequently parents or guardians do not recognize grandchildren born to children who elope. Guardians are people who are closest to women and they are absolutely visible both morally and materially (Suma, 2005).

According to the customs prevailing in society, marriage is not solely a personal matter concern as in the Western world, but marriage is also a matter of family, relatives, and society. The family or parties involved in the elopement incident must be responsible for resolving the matter. This is to avoid the emergence of prolonged disputes and harboring feelings of resentment or hurt between the two families.

The Muna ethnic community in resolving dopofuleighoo custom has many roles, including traditional figures and lebe (mosque employees) in the community. A traditional figure is someone who has a traditional position in an order of indigenous peoples in an area, with integrity, authority, and charisma being a role model for the entire community (Bastieng, 2020). The existence of traditional figures in marriage is to settle customary marital affairs such as elopement and determine the amount of dowry and fines imposed on the male family (according to the customs prevailing in the Muna ethnic community). Meanwhile, the lebe (mosque employee) is the person who is given the authority to hold religious ceremonies, including the marriage ceremony, so that the marriage becomes legal according to religious teachings. Imam is also defined as a person followed by mankind both as a leader and others (Bisri, 1999).

Niampe, L. et al. (2018) suggested that dopofuleighoo can occur for several reasons. Especially after the parents were officially notified of the marriage plans, but the girl's father still refused to permit the

marriage, Dopofuleighoo way of marriage could be done. The process is, when dopofuleighoo has occurred, the Imam then sends one or two modhi (mosque employers) to persuade the girl's father to allow his daughter to be married. If he refuses, then the modhi returns to the imam; and the imam reschedules the time for the modhi's meeting with the girl's father to persuade him again. If the meeting has happened three times and the girl's father still does not allow it, then the marriage is carried out by the imam who acts as the guardian of the girl. In this case, fines for elopement were not paid, and even kantaburi and kafeena were not paid. Because of this refusal, the girl's father lost the right of marriage guardian and he only received a dowry.

Referring to the process of elopement, starting from the agreement of the girl and the young man to elope until the implementation of elopement becomes legal in the Muna ethnic community, it is found that communication is the key in solving the elopement problem. Communication is the process of delivering messages or information from one person to another so that there is a common understanding (Mulyana, 2010). Communication is also carried out to influence others (Applbaum, 1974 in Rozikin, 2013). The young man communicated with the girl to ask for an elopement. After being at the place where the girl was rushed, communication was carried out, namely by the young man's family to the girl's family. Then completing the elopement custom, communication is also carried out, namely between the traditional leaders of the bride and groom. Furthermore, for the marriage process, communication is carried out by traditional leaders, priests, and both parties of the bride's family. The issue of elopement (dopofuleighoo) in the Muna tribal community is quite interesting because it can be resolved properly.

A communication strategy is a plan for the realization of the desired communication goals (Effendy, 2015). R. Wayne Pace et al. (in Abidin, 2015) mentions three central objectives of the communication strategy, namely: to ensure that the message is understood by the communicant (to secure understanding); for fostering the communicant through the message received (to establish acceptance); and to generate motivation (to motivate action). Effendy, (2007) in Wijaya (2015) argues, the preparation of communication strategies should pay attention to the components of communication, namely who will be the communicator or speaker, what is the purpose of communication, what methods/channels are used, and who is the communicant. Communication methods or techniques can be carried out in several ways, namely: informative communication, persuasive communication, coercive/instructive communication, and interpersonal human relations. Communication strategies must also pay attention to the language used, which is easy to understand and understand (Wijaya, 2015).

Communicators have a very important role in communication, namely source attractiveness and source credibility. Attractiveness can be built by creating an atmosphere where the communicant feels there is something in common with the communicator. While the credibility of the source is related to the profession or expertise of the communicator. Communicators must be

empathetic, namely positioning themselves with the communicant so that they can feel what they feel (Larisu et al., 2023). Therefore, it is important to conduct an in-depth study of the communication strategy used in solving the problem of elopement (*dopofuleighoo*) in the Muna ethnic community, because on the one hand it is considered to violate customs/religion but on the other hand it is still being carried out.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is located in Muna Regency, where in this location *dopofuleighoo* tradition is still carried out until now. This research includes qualitative case studies, which seek to explore and understand the meaning of several individuals or groups of people in depth. The object of the research is the communication strategy used by traditional figures in solving the problem of *dopofuleighoo* (elopement) tradition. Informants are determined purposively, namely, the person concerned has personal experience in accordance with the problems studied or has extensive knowledge about the problems studied. Research informants are traditional figures, *lebe*, *modhi*, *imam*, marriage officers from the government (KUA), and families/parents of the girls who have experienced elopement. Data was collected through in-depth interviews and document studies. Data processing techniques refer to qualitative research approaches and data analysis techniques refer to domain and taxonomy analysis (Cresswell, 2008). Checking the validity of research data using triangulation, namely triangulation with sources through (1) comparing observational data with interview data, (2) comparing what people say in public with what is said in private, (3) comparing what people say -people about the research situation with what they say all the time, (4) comparing the situation and perspective of a person with various opinions and views of people with different backgrounds, (5) comparing the results of interviews with the contents of a related document (Moleong, 2001).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Dopofuleighoo tradition in Muna ethnic community has been done since ancient times until now. Even though *dopofuleighoo* tradition in the Muna ethnic community is considered an act that violates customary law, violates parental authority, and undermines the honor of the girl's parents and relatives, some people do not care about it. It is proven that for couples who eloped, their family life is going well and the relationship between the two families is also harmonious. Of course this is inseparable from the communication strategy carried out by the parties involved in the elopement incident. As stated by one of the traditional figures who had completed an elopement (LI):

Dopofuleighoo tradition occurs for a reason and most of the reasons are caused by the woman's family, such as not giving permission, not getting a dowry, or because she is already pregnant. Therefore, after the occurrence of the *dopofuleighoo* tradition immediately communicated with all the families to find a way out. If not, the result will be that the problem will drag on and cause disharmony in the

relationship between women and their parents as well as in the behavior of men's families. The family should accept it sincerely and use it as a lesson. In particular, women's families can think of it as the fate of their children, because it is the children who will run their own household life and they certainly have an idea of how they will run their domestic life (Interview, 21 November 2023).

Based on the informant's statement that communication is a way to resolve *dopofuleighoo* tradition. Rogers & D. Lawrence Kincaid 1981 (Cangara, 2013), communication is a process in which two or more people form or exchange information with each other, which in turn will arrive at the same or deep mutual understanding. Hovland (Mulyana, 2010) says communication is a process of delivering messages from one person to another to influence their actions or behavior. The communication strategy is the best combination of all communication elements starting from the communicator, message, channel (media), and receiver to influence (effect) designed to achieve optimal communication goals (Wijaya, 2015).

Marriage in *dopofuleighoo* way is different from marriage in general. *dopofuleighoo* does not recognize the stages of proposing and introducing the two families according to formal rules. However, the process is carried out in several stages, namely: (1) Accepting the two prospective brides by hokumu (official Sarah agama); (2) Dopolele (Notifying the parents of the prospective bride); (3) Dengkoragho adhati Conducting customary deliberations; (4) Dengkoragho kafotangkano agama (Conducting administration according to Islamic religion); and (5) Kafokawi (Carrying out the marriage process). These stages are carried out by applying different communication strategies.

A. The Stage of receiving the two prospective brides by Sarah Religion Officer (Hokumu or Imam)

When the prospective groom carries away the prospective bride, the common destination is the house of o hokumu (Religious Sarah Employee). O hokumu (Sarah Religious Employees) in the Muna ethnic community are the organizers of marriages, both marriages through *dopofuleighoo* (elopement) and angka mata marriages (customary marriages) which are traditionally recognized by the Muna ethnic community. Before performing *dopofuleighoo*, the groom-to-be conveys to Hokumu. As the results of an interview with one of o hokumu who had received a candidate for elopement (LW), that: Before the two *dopofuleighoo* brides arrived, the groom-to-be came to the house to inform him that he would bring a woman as his future wife for marriage, including the time of arrival. Of course, the groom-to-be also conveys the reasons why he does *dopofuleighoo*. As a hokumu I have to accept it and solve the problem, because it has become part of my job (interview, 21 November 2023).

The explanation above shows that in the initial stage of *dopofuleighoo* process, the two prospective brides must inform the hokumu about their plan directly so that it is known and gets good respect from the hokumu. The hokumu's house was chosen for the two prospective brides

because it has a place to take refuge or shelter until the two prospective brides are completed/taken care of by custom until the marriage process is carried out. During *dopofuleighoo* process, a member of *hokumu* is obliged to protect the two prospective brides while completing the customary process that applies in *dopofuleighoo*. The length of their stay in *hokumu*'s house depends on the completion of the process carried out by all parties (*hokumu*, female family, male family, traditional figures). While in the house of *hokumu*, the prospective bride occupies one of the special rooms that have been prepared.

The initial stage to creating the same agreement between the speaker and the person being spoken to is direct face-to-face communication because this communication is immediately known and the feedback is understood (Devito, 2011).

B. The stage of informing the parents of the prospective bride and groom (doing *polele*)

Polele is the first process in delivering a message from the family of the prospective groom to the parents of the prospective bride after taking her fiancé away at the house of a *hokumu*. The contents of *polele*'s message are to notify a woman's parents about the loss of their daughter in *hokumu*'s house and to deliver a *dhandi* (promise) for the time of customary settlement (*sara-sara*). Doing *polele* to the female family is generally *o hokumu* appoints a delegation consisting of one or two people, while *polele* to the male side is the prospective groom himself or his family. As stated by one of the traditional figures of Muna (LI) that:

After receiving the two brides-to-be, the *hokumu* orders the groom-to-be to inform his parents or family about the *pofuleigho* event immediately. In addition, *hokumu* also sent two *polele* delegates to convey information on *dopofuleighoo* incident to the parents of the bride. From the results of submitting information to both male and female families, feedback will be obtained, generally, an agreement to complete the next stage of *adat* (Interview, 24 November 2023).

In *polele*, the groom's family generally responds more quickly than the woman's family, as well as in delivering the promise, the male family establishes themselves first before going to the female side. In the case of this promise, three stages of time are usually agreed upon, namely, five days, or ten days, or fifteen days, starting from the day of *polele* is held, or depending on the readiness of the prospective groom. It is clarified by *o hokumu* (LW) statement that:

The delegation consisted of 2 men who were on duty for *polele*, namely going to the house of the woman's parents to convey information that their daughter had been in *hokumu*'s house, which was underrun by a man (mentioning identity). Following up on this, the delegation conveyed the arrival of the male traditional delegation (to discuss customs) by giving *dhandi* (implementation time) (5, 10, or 15 days) (Interview, 24 November 2023).

Polele as an important step to complete *dopofuleighoo* process. Therefore, all aspects of communication need to be considered starting from the communicator (who speaks), the message, the

communicant (to whom to speak), the media or how to speak and what are the consequences or effects. In accordance with the Lasswell paradigm (Heryanto, 2020) that to measure the success of communication by answering the following questions: who, say what, to channel to whom with what effect. The parties who are the speakers in the *polele* are delegates who understand the problem of *dopofuleighoo* and are experts in conveying traditional messages in *dopofuleighoo*. Likewise, the language used is the local language of Muna under applicable customary rules. The communication technique applied is expected to be effective in solving *dopofuleighoo* problem and not causing problems. Based on experience, *dopofuleighoo* tradition was not born just like that, but there were causes and consequences so that sometimes delegates in customary talks got conflicts or differences or disagreements so that no agreement was built. If there is a conflict, *polele* delegation must make persuasive efforts until an agreement is found, even though it takes a long time because the purpose of marriage is a good life and can unite the two families in a harmonious life (*sakinah, mawaddah warahma*).

C. Conducting Customary Deliberation (*Dengkoragho Adhati*)

Conducting customary deliberation (*dengkoragho adhati*) in *dopofuleighoo* tradition is the stage of deliberation that is carried out under the decided time that has been agreed upon at the time of *polele*. The customary deliberation activity aims to unite views on the value of the customary unit of a count of marriage and marriage in the Muna ethnic (*bhoka*) or the amount of *bhoka* used by the bride and groom. The *bhoka* value is based on the *bhoka* value of each parent. If the value of the male's *bhoka* is higher than the female's *bhoka* value or has the same *bhoka* value, then the customary deliberation process runs well and smoothly. This is because in the marriage tradition of the Muna ethnic community if the customary value (*bhoka*) of men is higher than the customary value of women, it is followed by using the value of men's *bhoka* in marriage. In other cases, if the *bhoka* values are the same, then the men's *bhoka* values are still used in marriage.

Customary deliberation often complicates its implementation when the customary conflicting values of *bhoka* over the two customary delegates do not recognize each other, for example the value of *bhoka* for men is lower than the value of *bhoka* for women. This was emphasized by a traditional Muna leader (LI) that:

Dopofuleighoo traditional meetings sometimes find disputes because they are triggered by differences in the value of *bhoka*, for example, the value of the male *bhoka* is lower than the female *bhoka* value, so on the men's side, they object (do not accept) this value. Therefore, both parties again determine the time for deliberation if there is no agreement. A third party needs to be present to settle the difference in the value of the *bhoka* in question until an agreement is found. The third parties presented are generally traditional leaders who know the value of the customary marriage unit (*bhoka*) in the Muna tribe based on ancestral heritage (Interview, 24 November 2023).

This customary deliberation is a mandatory stage that cannot be skipped. This is the legacy of the parents. *Dengkoragho adhati* can run smoothly if both parties (parents of the bride and groom and the customary delegation) already have the same knowledge about the *bhoka* values of both parties. Therefore, in determining the speaker (communicator) in this case, the delegation needs to consider the expertise and experience of the delegates in order to be able to communicate well the traditional messages contained in the settlement of *dopofuleighoo* custom.

When *dengkoragho adhati* deliberations related to the determination of customary values (*bhoka*) have been completed, the next stage is the deliberation to determine the day of conducting and the financing of the wedding. Determination of the day of the wedding (*kakawi*) under the good day believed by the Muna tribe. Meanwhile, regarding the financing of marriage in the marriage custom of the Muna ethnic community, which is called *nifumano ifi* or more popularly referred to as money given to the parents of the prospective bride to be used at the party, it is entirely the burden of the groom's family.

D. Administrative Management by Religion (*Kafotangano Agama*)

Marriage administration is a stage that must be passed by the prospective bride and groom even if the marriage is with *dopofuleighoo* custom, so that the marriage is not only recognized by custom but also by law or applicable rules. This stage is carried out after the completion of *sara-sara* (custom) and the day of the marriage has been determined. The bride and groom are obliged to take care of the administration of marriage registration to fulfill the legal and religious elements. As stated by the Marriage Registration Officer of Wapunto Village (LG) that:

Dopofuleighoo tradition even though some people don't agree with it, needs to get legal and religious recognition. One of them is taking care of the entire marriage administration so that it has legal force so that it is clear that the husband and wife relationship that is built is officially recognized by the state (Interview, 25 November 2023).

Likewise, it was conveyed by a couple who had done *dopofuleighoo* (WH) that: Even though we married in *dopofuleighoo* way, we also hope to have legal recognition before the law regarding our marriage bond as is the case with marriages in general (Interview, 26 November 2023).

The process of managing marriage administration in *dopofuleighoo* marriage custom in the Muna ethnic community is called *kafotangkano agama* (religious strengthening). Marriage administration arrangements are generally carried out at the local Religious Affairs Office (KUA), under article 3 of the Regulation of the Minister of Religion Number 34 2016 paragraph (1) that the implementation of services, supervision, recording and reporting of marriage and reconciliation can be carried out at the KUA Office. Of course, in this arrangement, the two brides and grooms come to the KUA Office by bringing all the requirements that have been determined. Proof of

marriage administration in the form of a marriage certificate and recorded as a new couple. Marriages registered by the administration show that the marriage has legal force (Latupono, 2019).

E. Implementation of the Marriage Process (*Kafokawi*)

The implementation of the marriage process (*kafokawi*) in *dopofuleighoo* tradition is conducted if all the processes of customary requirements and religious (*kafotangkano agama*) have been completed. *Kafokawi* is conducted according to the day that has been agreed upon in the customary deliberation. The procession of conducting the marriage is under the customary stages that have been generally agreed upon and under religious provisions and applicable regulations.

In the marriage custom with *dopofuleighoo* tradition in the Muna ethnic community, the man's family is fully responsible for its implementation and the implementation of *kafokawi* is conducted in the *hokumu*'s house occupied at the time of *dopofuleighoo* process, as well as in other places, such as in the male family's house or family house girls (with a party or not party). The results of the *hokumu* (LW) interview are as follows:

Dopofuleighoo tradition is not always a bad thing, even though I impliedly don't want my children and family to do that. However, *dopofuleighoo* tradition has been regulated (approved by the ancestors) so this is not something taboo (forbidden or shameful). The proof is that in Muna there are still quite a few people who are even married in this way. For us, as customary organizers (Sarah employees) it's a common thing and we usually handle it, of course with the process that is passed under applicable customs, as well as the need for good communication between parties from the beginning of the process to the end of the process (marriage contract) (Interview, 27 November 2023).

Based on the quote above, it shows that *dopofuleighoo* tradition in the Muna ethnic community does not always have a bad meaning, so this is not taboo or forbidden so it can be celebrated or not, as long as the custom regulates it. Some of the people of Muna ethnic community accept this marriage in *dopofuleighoo* way but some avoid it. For those who accept it because it is one of the alternatives for an immediate marriage which is considered to be an obstacle for the bride and groom, as a result of the prospective bride's parents wanting a big party, or one of the parents of the prospective groom or bride does not approve of them, or differences in status, social life, or the parents of the bride and groom delaying their marriage, or the woman was pregnant before marriage, or there is a love triangle (Aso, L. et al, 2022). While those who refuse, assess marriage in *dopofuleighoo* way as a marriage that is not in accordance with religious law or applicable formal rules.

As long as marriages in *dopofuleighoo* way in the Muna ethnic community are still being carried out, so far the marriage processes can be completed. Communication is one of the strategies that can be a media to solve *dopofuleighoo* problem in the Muna ethnic community because at the stages of completing the marriage it involves communication with various parties such as

traditional figures communicating with women's families when they are first conveyed by *hokumu*. There are *dopofuleighoo* couples or mediating if they are married. there is a problem in the process of settling *dopofuleighoo* marriage custom. O *hokumu* is the person who is responsible for solving *dopofuleighoo* problem from the beginning to the marriage process and is responsible for the legal marriage process according to religious regulations. In carrying out its role, *o hokumu* will communicate with prospective grooms and brides and communicate with traditional figures if there are customary problems. Traditional figures also communicate with women's and men's families during the process of settling *dopofuleighoo* custom. Likewise, the prospective bride and groom communicate with the marriage administration registrar to obtain a certificate of the validity of their marriage.

The communication process that takes place in *dopofuleighoo* marriage process is face-to-face communication or through direct intermediaries to obtain a common understanding between the two parties (Mulyana, 2010) and to ensure that the message is understood by the communicant, or the message can be received, or the message can provide motivation. to be approved (Effendy, 2007). While communication strategies or techniques are generally carried out, communication is informative and persuasive, while coercive is rarely. In line with what Effendy (2015) stated, the communication strategy is informative if it only conveys information, persuasive if you find a response that requires more explanation than the message conveyed, and coercive/coercive if you don't find the same understanding even though it has been repeatedly conveyed. Marriage in *dopofuleighoo* way, although initially, it was not well received by the woman's family, with the right communication strategy approach, was finally accepted and agreed to be resolved until the marriage was legally carried out.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results and discussion of the research, it can be concluded that marriage through *dopofuleighoo* process some people accept as one of the marriage customs carried out in the Muna ethnic community. Completion of *dopofuleighoo* marriage takes five stages, namely (1) submission of the prospective groom to *Sarah agama/hokumu* (mosque employee) regarding the implementation of *dopofuleighoo* and *hokumu* to receive the two prospective brides; (2) conveying information about *dopofuleighoo* incident to the parents of the prospective bride (doing *polele*); (3) conducting customary deliberations to settle the marriage of *dopofuleighoo* (*dengkoragho adhati*); (4) Completion of administration according to religion regulation (*kafotangano agama*); and (5) Conducting of marriage process (*Kafokawi*). At these stages dominantly the traditional figures use informative and persuasive communication strategies, while coercive communication strategies are rarely used because marriage is expected by both parties and there is no coercion between one another. It is expected that marriage through *dopofuleighoo* way

will not often be used as a shortcut for the bride and groom. Marriage with a proposal process or prior introduction by both families must be an option to become a bride and groom.

Acknowledgment

Thank you to all the team who have worked so hard and thank you to everyone involved in this research. Thank you very much.

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